

**AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF RECURRENT ARSHA IN AN ELDERLY PATIENT: A
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ABSTRACT

Arsha is a commonly observed ano-rectal conditions in Ayurvedic practice, mainly attributed to weakened diigestive fire and imbalance of *Doshas*. Recurrence after surgical treatment is frequently noted, especially among elderly patients suffering from standing constipation and unhealthy dietary patterns. this case report present an 82-year-old male with recurring hemorrhoid complaints one year past-surgery. The patient exhibited symptoms such as rectal bleeding, Pricking sensation, Constipation, Prolapse of mass, and associated lower back pain. Ayurvedic evaluation suggested a predominance of *Vata Dosha* along with involvement of *Rakta*. The management included classical Ayurvedic medications, matra basti therapy and local application. Gradual and noticeable improvement was observed in bleeding, discomfort, and bowel function. Clinical images also substantiated the theraopetic response. This case highlights the effectiveness of Ayurvedic intervention in the management of recurrent *Arsha*

KEYWORDS: Arsha, Heamorrhoids, Ayurveda, Rakta Dusti, Vata Dosha, Bast.**INTRODUCTION**

Arsha is described in classical literature as a pathological condition characterized by the development of fleshy growths in the anal region, leading to symptoms such as pain, bleeding, and discomfort during defecation. the disease is mainly attributed to Agnimandya and vitiation of *Vata Dosha*, often associated with Rakta involvement. In modern medicine, *Arsha* is comparable to hemorrhoids, which are enlarged vascular cushion whitin the anal canal that become symptomatic when inflamed or engorged. Hemorrhoids are generally categorized into internal and external types, and further further classified accoeding to the extent of prolapse.^[1]

The clinical manifestations include rectal bleeding, protrusion, irritation, and pain during defecation. While surgical interventions such as hemorrhoidectomy can

offer symptomatic relief, the likelihood of recurrence remains considerable, especially in elderly patients due to persistent constipation and age -related degenerative changes.^[2]

Ayurveda adopts a comprehensive and root cause-oriented approach in the management of *Arsha*, focusing not only symptomatic relief but also on correction of the underlying pathology. The shaman chikista involve *Deepan*, *Pachan*, and *Vatanuloman* Along with intervention aimed at controlling bleeding and reducing inflammation. Among the panchakarma procedures, *Basti* therapy is considered particularly effective in pacifying aggravated *Vata Dosha*. In addition, local applications play a supportive role in alleviating inflammation and promoting tissue healing.^[3,4]

MATERIALS AND METHOD

This case study was carried out on an 82-year-old male patient who presented recurrent symptoms of Arsha. The patient had a prior history of surgical management for the same condition one year earlier. A thorough clinical evaluation was performed using both Ayurvedic principles and contemporary diagnostic methods. This was an observational case study conducted to evaluate the therapeutic effect of Ayurvedic intervention in the management of recurrent Arsha.

Case presentation

Age- 82 year
Gender- male
Past History- Surgical treatment for hemorrhoids one year ago

Chief complaints

Internal bleeding per rectum
Pricking sensation in anal region
Constipation
Prolapsed hemarrhoidal mass
Low back pain

History of present illness

The patient reported recurrence of symptoms over the post one year following previous surgical intervention. Complaints included bleeding during defecation, discomfort, and incomplete evacuation of bowels.

Dietary History

Frequent consumptions of tea
Regular intake of dates
Irregular dietary pattern with low fiber intake

Ashtavidha pariksha

Nadi – Vata predominant, Tikshna, kshina
Mala- irregular, unsatisfactory
Mutra- increased frequency
Jivha-sama (coated)
Kshudha- Irregular
Nidra- Normal

Photos

Figure 1: Before Treatment.

Vitals

Blood pressure- 60/100 mmof hg
Pulse rate-17beat per minute
Weight- 55kl

Local examination

Prolapsed, congested lobulated haemorrhoidal mass observed externally
Type- mixed hemorrhoids
Grade-3 prolapse
Proctoscopy-internal hemorrhoidal at 3,7, and 11 o clock position with mucosal edema and prolapse

Diagnosis- Vatpradhan Arsha with Rakta Dusti

Samprapti- Dietary and lifestyle factors also age factor such as excessive intake of Tea, irregular eating habit, and insufficient fiber consumption led to impairment of *Agni* and aggravation of *Vata Dosha*. This resulted in chronic constipation and increased pressure in the anorectal region. The involvement of *Rakta* and *Mamsa Dhatu* contributed to the formation and progression of *Arsha* in the *Guda* region.^[5]

Materials- The treatment regimen comprised shaman, shodhan, and local modalities.^[6]

Shaman chikista

Arshakuthar Rasa-2 tablet -twice daily before meals
Triphala Guggul-2 table- twice daily before meals
Abhayarishta-10ml- mixed with equal quantity of water after meals
Kandudha Rasa-2 table- three times a day (to be chewed)
Shodhan chikista
Panchakarma intervention included administration of *matra basti* with *chicha lavan tail* once weekly, 60ml.

Local therapy

In additional *Shatadhauta Ghrita* was advised for local application over the affected region
Treatment upto given 15 days only.

Figure 2: After Treatment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The patient demonstrated progressive improvement throughout the treatment period. During the initial week

of treatment, a clear decrease in per rectal bleeding was noted. the pricking sensation and pain during defecation were markedly reduced. bowel movement become more

regular, constipation was relieved. By the second week, there was a noticeable reduction in the size of the prolapsed mass, and no further episodes of bleeding were reported. low back pain showed more good improvement.

Applied *Matra basti* played a significant role in normalizing *Apan vata*, thereby improving bowel habits and minimizing strain. Local application supported wound healing and reduced inflammation in the affected area.

The final outcome is the follow-up evaluation suggested sustained symptomatic relief, with no recurrence during the observation period. clinical image further confirmed the reduction in swelling and improvement in the condition of local tissues.

DISCUSSION

The present case highlights the effectiveness of ayurvedic management in recurrent *Arsha*. The ayurvedic approach focuses on correcting *Agni*, balancing *Vata Dosha*, and relieving constipation, which is primary etiological factor, specifically disturbed *apan vata* play a crucial role in the development of *Arsha* by causing dryness constipation and increase the pressure in the anorectal region, thereby promoting recurrence.

The treatment approach in this case was aimed at: *Arshakuthar ras* its help to impaired *Agni*, reduce *Ama* formation and correction the root cause of *Arsha* *Kamdudha ras* it helps in reducing bleeding, it mainly *Rakta stambhaka*

Triphala guggul has mild laxative helping relieve constipation and easing bowel movement, supports wound healing and prevent infection.^[7]

Abhayarishhta used for chronic constipation and *vata* regulation also it is *rogadhikar* of *Arsha*

Matra basti of *chinchha lavan tail* it has *lavan* and *aamla ras* is there so its help to managing *vata* disorders, played a role in restoring the normal function of *Apan Vata*.^[8]

CONCLUSION

Ayurvedic management proved beneficial in managing recurrent *Arsha* in this elderly patient. The treatment not only alleviated symptoms but also addressed the underlying cause. This approach may serve as a safe and effective option in chronic and recurrently cases. the efficacy of Ayurvedic therapy in the management of recurrent *Arsha*, especially in geriatric patients where relapse after surgical procedures is frequently observed. the administration of classical Ayurvedic formulation along with *Matra basti* and local application not only alleviated symptoms such as bleeding, pain and prolapse but also the underlying pathophysiology of the condition. Ayurveda adopts a holistic approach by addressing the root cause, thereby minimizing the likelihood of recurrence. this case supports that a properly planned Ayurvedic regimen can serve as a safe

effective, and sustainable option for managing recurrent *Arsha*.

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